

Optimising Arctic Observational Capacities

Rapid climate change in the Arctic demands a coherent observing system that optimises the use of existing resources through collaborative planning and shared practices.

Key Challenges

Arctic climate change and its effects on the natural and human environment are best documented by long-term observations and Indigenous Knowledge. These data are also necessary for sustainable, ecosystem-based management and support decision-makers in making knowledge-based decisions for people and the environment.

 International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT), a network of research stations in the Arctic, boreal and alpine regions, offers a platform for research and monitoring.

 The Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) is the main international program that keeps track of changes in frozen ground, known as permafrost.

 Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO). The DBOs are interdisciplinary marine observatories tracking the impact of changing environmental drivers on Arctic marine ecosystems.

 Sea ice from Sept 1, 2024

However, Arctic observations are currently limited in time and in the area they cover. Data are often stored in different, sometimes incompatible, formats, or are difficult to access. Making on-site observations is logistically challenging and expensive, while satellite observations struggle with observations under cloud, snow and sea ice.

Funding of observatories and time series is often managed within national or institutional programmes, or short-term projects, adding to the fragmentation of the current observational system. For decision-making, several approaches can help make research more accessible, understandable, and tailored to local needs.

Recommendations

Collaboration

- **Strengthen collaboration across borders and disciplines:** Encourage teamwork across scientific fields, national borders, and cultures, with enhanced inclusion of Indigenous Knowledge and local observations, to build a more holistic understanding of Arctic change.
- **Create spaces for sharing and learning:** Invest in networks where people can share data, ideas, and experiences. Every contribution - no matter how small - can add up to big progress when people work together.
- **Build a collaborative future:** Involve early-career researchers and local people and promote pan-Arctic knowledge partnerships to strengthen our collective understanding of the Arctic system.

Optimisation

- **Make the most of what we already have:** Improve coordination networks for more harmonised use of existing observing systems, leading to comprehensive and useful environmental information, for the benefit of all - society and science.
- **Facilitate reuse of data:** Improve routines for sharing standardised data to support broader usage.

Funding

- **Support sustainable funding:** Advocate for well-coordinated funding that secures continuous high-quality observations for tracking changes and impacts. This includes the maintenance and long-term operation of key infrastructure platforms.

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